

GITA¹ : THE SOLUTION

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“Gita”, the Glorious Song sung @ the battlefield of Kurukshetra by none other than Lord Krishna Himself, for whom Veda VyAsa aptly said “कृष्णास्तु भगवान स्वयं |” that Krishna Himself is God.

Preached to disciple warrior Arjuna during wartime; “The Song Divine”, the world’s only philosophy in singing fashion reminds us of the phrase –

“Nero playing Flute, while Rome was burning”

Almighty is cool, quiet, calm and tranquil. In His eyes¹, there is nothing like problem!! Therefore He says: “नेहाभिक्रमनाशोऽस्ति प्रत्यवायो न विध्यते |” [2, 40]

However, even if He sees from our eyes; then also Gita has the solution for mankind. Be it @ individual level or @ the levels of family, society or Nation. Be it of the nature of Political, Economic, Social or Psychological. Or be it of the type of Ancient or Modern, contemporary or traditional. There is one for everyone! One size fits all!! Gita gives The solution. How? Let us have a glance...

Sr.	Our Problem	Sr.	Gita’s Solution	Ch.	St.
1	I am too young, what can I do?	1	ममैवांशो जीवलोके जीवभूत सनातनः No, you are my son; Lion’s son is always Lion. So, don’t worry.	15	07
2	But I am a woman. अबला	2	स्त्रियो वैश्यास्तथा शूद्रास्तेऽपि यान्ति परां गतिम् You still are eligible for the liberation. [मुक्ति]	09	32
3	I am confused. Depressed. In dilemma...	3	सर्वधर्मान्परित्यज्य मामेकं शरणं व्रज Just come to My surrender.	18	66

¹ i.e. from His perspective

4	I am an atheist निरीश्वरवादी	4	ये यथा मां प्रपद्यन्ते तांसतथैव भजाम्यहं । You still will come to me only	04	11
5	I am too old now, All my time has gone away, I don't see any hope in me.	5	बहूनां जन्मनामन्ते ज्ञानवान् मां प्रपद्यते । Even though, we lose hope from ourselves, He never!	07	19
6	I am not going to give my everything	6	स्वल्पमप्यस्य धर्मस्य त्रायते महतो भयात् । You sacrifice just a little	02	40
7	Why bad things happen with good people only?	7	... गहना कर्मणो गतिः ॥ “Law of Karma” is very subtle	04	17
8	I am not a Hindu, nor am I born in India.	8	कर्मण्येवाधिकारस्ते मा फलेषु कदाचन । U do your best... He'll do the rest	02	47
9	I am a poor person. I have no money for performing rituals	9	पत्रं पुष्पं फलं तोयं यो मे भक्त्या प्रयच्छति । I see intentions behind action	09	26
10	What if I die midway? Will all my efforts go in vein?	10	शुचीनांश्रीमतांगेहे योगभ्रष्टोऽभिजायते ।	06	41

		You will continue... ... from where you have stopped		
11	Is there a solution to terrorism?	11 अहिंसा परमो धर्म [महाभारत] ... नायं हन्ति न हन्यते अधर्म धर्ममिति या ... Misrepresenting doctrines instead of their right spirit	02 18	19 31
12	सर्वारंभो हि दोषेण ... If every action is associated with दोष, why at all should one do any action?	12 a. You can't remain w/o action b. Do it for the sack of society न मे पार्थास्ति कर्तव्यं त्रिषु लोकेषु किञ्चन	03	22
13	How can I get the true peace of mind?	13 ... स शान्तिमधिगच्छति Through self-control	02	71
14	How to sustain with the pace of this competitive world?	14 ... योगः कर्मषु कौशलम् You completion is with you only. Practice more & be skilful..	02	50
15	We feel, our efforts are not enough for fighting against the evil forces of this world	15 यदा यदा हि धर्मस्य... ...संभवामि युगेयुगे Time and again, I'll come 4 sure	04	07

16	Is there any environmental solution including that of 'Global Warming'?	16	यद्यद्विभूतिमत्सत्त्वं श्रीमद्ूर्जितमेव वा Use, but do not exploit resources	10	41
17	How to manage 'Work-Life Balance'?	17	अभ्यासेन तु कौन्तेय वैराग्येण च ... By regular practice and renunciation	03	35
18	How to secure my future	18	तद्विद्धि प्रणिपातेन परिप्रश्नेन सेवया As such, time is non-divisible	04	34

Due to the limitation of resources, especially the time @ our disposal; only few questions are taken. Consider them as the representative. However, it is certain that –

- As there is no end to human problems...
So too there is no end to the solution offered by Shrimad Bhagawad Gita
- One can overcome these problems by implementing religiously, the solution as preached by Bhagawad Gita
- In subtler thinking, everything is illusion [माया]. This life is a big dream and there is, as such no problem at all.

We all are potentially divine and came here on this earth just to enjoy.

So, DON'T worry, just be HAPPY; simply by following the Gita's way of life.

ॐ तत् सत् |

References:

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